

Statistic Analysis of the Brand Consultants Market at the United Arab Emirates and Ukraine: Indicators, Peculiarities and Trends

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Abstract

The article is aimed the substantiation and an analysis of major trends brands consult services at the United Arab Emirates and Ukraine. The criteria for measurement of brand consults business process have been examined. The analysis of the branding agencies activities from the perspective of the external and internal factors impact of the business environment is carried out. Through the present work, the evolution components of the brand consultants according to the international rankings were analyzed together with the comparative analysis of the main trends of the both countries.

Key words: brand, international ratings, brand consultants market

Introduction

The conceptual understanding of the brand is based on the relationship of such components as: carrier, identity, philosophy. The bearer of the brand can be industrial and non-industrial products, services, organization, person (group of persons), territory, state. That is, the formation and management of the brand should be considered in terms of various phenomena and processes in the market B2C, B2B, B2G, C2G. Extremely important role in understanding the brand are the processes of consumption and psychology of consumer's behavior, trust and loyalty on the part of the consumer to the brand. All this requires the involvement of professionals, specialists working in branding agencies in the development and management of brands.

The development of modern technologies has led to the emergence of many new products and services with an IT component that requires the use of new branding technologies, advertising and PR technologies. Therefore, indicators, peculiarities and cross-category trends monitoring of the brand consultants market at United Arab Emirates and Ukraine is important and relevant

Materials and methods

As a methodological basis for the research was used the information and analytical materials of the international rating agencies. To achieve the research goal, methods of scientific abstraction, comparative and structural analysis and synthesis, and systematic approach were used.

The external components of the branding agencies activities are analyzed in such aspects as: market size (small business, midmarket, and enterprise), industry and service focus of the branding agencies. The internal components of the United Arab Emirates and Ukraine branding agencies activity such are analyzed in such aspects of the business processes: project size, cost of consulting services, number of staff, brand services focus (corporate identity, brand strategy, product branding, brand communication, naming).

The contemporary strengths and weakness for brand consultants have been systematized. According to the different expert's points of view, the main components of a successful brand and cross-category social-communicating and economics trends has determined as: the refocus of the people life's priorities, quality of life, culture, creativity, sharing experience, business (innovations and investment), combination of traditional marketing communications tools and social media tools for the trade, e-Commerce, omni-shopper activity, the right mix of cross-functional staff for business process.

Results and discussion

Fundamental research on branding is devoted to the works of many foreign authors, the most famous of which are the works of Keller K., LePla J., Davis S. V., Parker L. M., McDonald M., Mouncey P. [1-3]. Most authors study the brand as a complex phenomenon based on a combination of tangible and intangible components.

The processes of globalization give the concept of «brand» more and more properties, manifestations and areas of implementation, competition increasing [4]. Therefore, special attention should be paid to such components added to the classical 4P concept as people and processes. Scientists and practitioners point to the limitations of the classical concept of 4P: product, price, place, promotion. Therefore, in modern conditions at the marketing, management, branding we use the 7P, 12P concepts.

It is determined that people (consumers and employees), processes (business processes, communication processes) are extremely relevant to the brand management. Branding agencies take the main role at those activities. Branding agency's staff has necessary skills, help to create, manage and develop the brand, thus fulfilling their responsibilities and promises to consumers. B2C, B2B, B2G, C2G market players, such as customers, business partners and other stakeholders (for example government) interact with the brand. Therefore, the brand concept and brand philosophy, well-balanced and flexible brand communications system requires the application of a professional approach and the branding agencies activities, which help to reach high quality level of the brand building.

According to information about the top Branding agencies their numbers at Jul 2020 where: 13 agencies in the United Arab Emirates and 15 agencies in Ukraine [5]. Such agency's numbers is evaluable for a comparative analysis.

The results of the company's analysis through the prism of business size (medium, small and large businesses) are represented at the Tables 1, 2.

Tab 1: Client Focus of the Top United Arab Emirates Brand Consultants (Jul 2020)

Brand Rank	Company Name	Midmarket (\$10M – \$1B)	Small business (<\$10M)	Enterprise (>\$1B)
1	Jpd ts	60	20	20
2	Start Design	100	0	0
3	DarkHoney OÜ	60	30	10
4	Ziad Al Halabi	50	50	0
5	Iktomi	–	–	–
6	Tonnit Design	–	–	–
7	Webperts	50	50	0
8	E Direct	20	65	15
9	Digital Marketing Agency TrustCorp	–	–	–

10	Generator	–	–	–
11	Xpezia	35	55	10
12	202 Media & Events	–	–	–
13	WebCastle Technologies LLC	–	–	–

Table is created by authors according to [5]

There is no available information (Table 1) about some UAE agencies: «Iktomi», «Tonnit Design», «Digital Marketing Agency TrustCorp», «Generator», «202 Media & Events», «WebCastle Technologies LLC».

The results of the Ukrainian company's analysis according to business size (medium, small and large businesses) are represented at the Table 2.

Tab 2: Client Focus Top Ukrainian Brand Consultants (Jul 2020)

Brand Rank	Company Name	Midmarket (\$10M – \$1B)	Small business (<\$10M)	Enterprise (>\$1B)
1	Admind Agency	20	20	60
2	Gram	–	–	–
3	Tubik Studio	25	50	25
4	Brain Tank	70	25	5
5	Bambuk Studio	40	40	20
6	711 Media	50	5	45
7	Leletko&Pronyk	30	70	0
8	Rubarb Digital	–	–	–
9	Twid	50	30	20
10	Clear Art	–	–	–
11	Boostbase Group	30	60	10
12	Respect.Studio	20	80	0
13	Daviann	20	80	0
14	Belka Studio	–	–	–
15	Deco.Agency	–	–	–

Table is created by authors according to [5]

There is no available information about some Ukrainian agencies: «Rubarb Digital», «Clear Art», «Belka Studio», «Deco.Agency» (Table 2).

Midmarket. Among the 13 UAE top brand consultants, 7 agencies (53,8%) work at midmarket. The share of the serviced companies by the relevant agencies is 20–60%. In Ukraine, among the 15 top brand consultants, 10 agencies (66,7%) work at midmarket. The share of the serviced companies by the relevant agencies is 20-70%.

Small business. Among the 13 UAE top brand consultants, 6 agencies (46,2%) deal with small business. The share of the serviced companies by the relevant agencies is 20-65%. In Ukraine, among the 15 top brand consultants, 10 (66,7%) work at midmarket. The share of the serviced companies by the relevant agencies is 20-80%.

Enterprise. Among the 13 UAE top brand consultants, 4 agencies (30,7%) work with big business (big enterprises, companies). The share of the serviced companies by the relevant agencies is 10-20%. In Ukraine, among the 15 top brand consultants, 6 agencies (46,7%) work with big business (big enterprises, companies). The share of the serviced companies by the relevant agencies is 10–60%.

It is noted that more share branding agencies at the midmarket are at the Ukraine compared the UAE (66,7% та 53,8% corresponded). **The same situation is about small business.** The shares of leading branding agencies for the Enterprise in Ukraine and the UAE are 46,7% and 30,7%, corresponded (Table 3).

The share of the projects, which have done for midmarket and small business in the UAE and Ukraine is 20-80%. The share of the projects, which have done for the big business at the UAE is 10-20% and for the big business at the Ukrainian is 10-60%.

Tab 3: Projects characteristics implemented by the leaders of United Arab Emirates and Ukrainian Brand Consultants corresponded to business size (Jul 2020)

Indicators	United Arab Emirates	Ukraine
Midmarket (\$10M - \$1B)		
brand consultants share, %	53,8	66,7
projects share, %	20-60	20-70
Small business (<\$10M)		
brand consultants share, %	46,2	66,7
projects share, %	20-65	20-80
Enterprise (>\$1B)		
brand consultants share, %	30,7	46,7
projects share, %	10-20	10-60

Table is created by authors according to [5]

According to the results of the analysis, in the Ukraine branding agencies serve a large number of the big enterprises. The share of serviced enterprises in Enterprise UAE is 10-20% and Ukraine is 10-60%. That is, in Ukraine, branded agencies serve a large number of large enterprises. Research the authors of this article allows to analyze brand consultants according to such characteristics: min project size, avg. hourly rate, employees (Table. 4).

Tab 4: Some indicators of the internal brand consultants business processes at the United Arab Emirates and Ukraine (Jul 2020)

Indicators	United Arab Emirates		Ukraine	
	Total Top Brand Consultants numbers	Share Total Top Brand Consultants %	Total Top Brand Consultants numbers	Share Total Top Brand Consultants %
Min project size (\$)				
50,000+	0	0	1	6,67
25,000+	1	7,69	0	0
10,000+	2	15,38	1	6,67
5,000+	3	23,07	6	40,0
1,000+	6	46,17	6	40,0
Non information	1	7,69	1	6,67
Total	13	100	15	100
Avg. hourly rate (\$/ hr.)				
150 – 199	1	7,69	0	0
100 – 149	1	7,69	1	6,67
50 – 99	3	23,07	1	6,67
25 – 49	2	15,41	11	73,32
< 25	3	23,07	1	6,67

Undisclosed	3	23,07	1	6,67
Total	13	100	15	100
Employees				
50 – 249	3	23,07	2	13,34
10 – 49	6	46,17	11	73,32
2 – 9	3	23,07	1	6,67
Freelancer	1	7,69	1	6,67
Total	13	100	15	100

Table is created by authors according to [5]

Projects implemented by branding agencies range in size from \$ 50,000 to \$ 1,000. It should be noted that in the UAE the small projects have budget \$ 1,000+ and have the largest share (46,17%).

The authors found that in Ukraine the projects worth \$ 1,000+ and \$ 5,000+ have largest share (40,0%). According to the results of research, the cost of consulting services depends mainly on the total cost of the project and the experience of the branding agency is determined. The high total project cost corresponds to the project risks and consulting services prices.

In particular, at the UAE, the largest projects share (23,07%) has consulting services price less than 25 \$/hr. and 50–99 \$/hr. In Ukraine, the largest projects share (73,32%) has consulting services price 25–49 (\$/hr.) (Table 4).

It is determined, that despite the international activities of most branding agencies, which were considered, the cost of relevant consulting services is lower in Ukraine. This is directly depended on rather difficult economic situation and lower staff salary in Ukraine compared to the UAE.

The staff number is an important characteristic of the branding agencies internal business processes, which was discussed at the beginning of this article. The staff number which necessary for the project realization is a factor that determines the volume of orders. In other words, the staff number, as well as competence and skills determines the speed and quality of the internal agency business processes, and staff number is an indicator of the branding agency capacity [4]. In the UAE, among the leaders [1] 46,17% of the branding agencies have 10-49 employees. The share of very small (2–9 persons) or very large (50–249 persons) branding agencies is about a quarter (23,07%). In Ukraine, among the leaders [1] the most branding agencies (73,32%) have 10–49 employees. The share of branding agencies which has a large number of employees (50–249 persons) is 13,34%.

The most popular brand management directions are: corporate identity, brand strategy, product branding, brand communication, naming. The results of analysis of the branding focus at the United Arab Emirates are represented at the Tables 5, 6.

Tab 5: Branding focus United Arab Emirates Brand Consultants (Jul 2020), %

Brand Agency Name	Corporate identity	Brand strategy	Product branding	Brand messaging	Naming	Total, %
1) Jpd Brand Strategy & Design Consultants	40	43	8	7	2	100
2) Start Design	100	0	0	0	0	100
3) DarkHoney OÜ	20	20	20	20	10	100
4) Ziad Al Halabi	75	25	0	0	0	100
5) Iktomi	30	40	0	10	20	100
6) Tonnit Design	50	20	10	10	10	100
7) Webperts	30	40	10	10	10	100

8) E Direct	45	20	10	15	10	100
9) Digital Marketing Agency TrustCorp*	–	–	–	–	–	–
10) Generator*	–	–	–	–	–	–
11) Xpezia	20	20	20	20	20	100
12) 202 Media & Events	25	25	25	25	-	100
13) WebCastle Technologies LLC*	–	–	–	–	–	–

Table is created by authors according to [5] * No available datas

The most popular brand management directions in Ukraine are: corporate identity, brand strategy, product branding (Table 6). Naming is the least popular branding focus directions in both countries (Table 5, 6).

Tab 6: Branding focus Top Ukrainian Brand Consultants (Jul 2020)

Brand Agency Name	Corporate identity	Brand strategy	Product branding	Brand messaging	Naming	Total, %
1) Admind Agency	40	20	20	10	10	100
2) Gram	50	0	50	0	0	100
3) Tubik Studio	50	0	50	0	0	100
4) Brain Tank	15	50	20	10	5	100
5) Bambuk Studio	30	15	30	15	10	100
6) 711 Media*	–	–	–	–	–	–
7) Leletko&Pronyk	40	20	20	20		100
8) Rubarb Digital*	–	–	–	–	–	–
9) Twid*	–	–	–	–	–	–
10) Clear Art	70	10	20	-	-	100
11) Boostbase Group*	–	–	–	–	–	–
12) Respect.Studio*	–	–	–	–	–	–
13) Daviann	20	40	10	20	10	100
14) Belka Studio*	–	–	–	–	–	–
15) Deco.Agency	80	0	10	0	10	100

Table is created by authors according to [5] * No available datas

The corporate identity improvement, brand strategy development, product branding, creation of the effective brand communications through which the brand talks to the clients, effective naming are urgent strategic objectives for companies at the various economic activity directions.

However, globalization and integration processes, competition, which intensifies even more with the development of digital technologies have determined brand consultants industry focus.

According to the results of the research, all types of economic activities of the branding projects are systematized in some groups according to business.

The ranking analysis directions of the United Arab Emirates Brand Consultants (Table 7) allowed to determine 4 groups of the agencies.

For example Group 1 is represented by agencies which deal the projects in such directions as:

1.1 *Information technology* («Webperts» (7), «E Direct» (8), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9), «Generator» (10)). The projects share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 25%.

1.2 *Real estate* («Ziad Al Halabi» (4) «Webperts» (7), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9), «Generator» (10)). The projects share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 25%.

1.3 *Consumer products & services* («Jpd Brand Strategy & Design Consultants») (1), «Webperts» (7), «Digital Marketing Agency TrustCorp» (9), «Generator» (10)). The projects share of at the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 20%.

Tab 7: Industry focus Top United Arab Emirates Brand Consultants (Jul 2020)

Group	Industry focus	Agency numbers	Agency's rank	Agency's Share, %	Project's share at the total agency's projects portfolio %	
					Min	Max
1	1.1 Information technology	4	7,8,9,10	26,7	7	25
	1.2 Real estate	4	4,7,9,10		7	25
	1.3 Consumer products & services	4	1,7,9,10		7	20
2	2.1 Financial services	3	2,9,10	20,0	7	30
	2.2 Advertising & marketing	3	7,8,9		7	30
	2.3 Retail	3	1,2,4		7	30
	2.4 Ecommerce	3	7,8,9		7	20
	2.5 Arts, entertainment & music	3	7,4,10		10	25
3	3.1 Hospitality & leisure	2	1,7	13,3	10	50
	3.2 Media	2	7,8		10	25
	3.3 Telecommunications	2	2,7		10	20
	3.4 Business services	2	4,9		8	25
	3.5 Manufacturing	2	1,9		7	12
	3.6 Energy & natural resources	2	1,9		7	15
4	4.1 Educational	1	10	6,67	30	

Table is created by authors according to [5]

Group 2 is represented by agencies which deal the projects in such directions as:

2.1 *Financial services* («Start Design» (2), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9), «Generator» (10)). The projects share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 30%.

2.2 *Advertising & marketing* («Webperts» (7), «E Direct» (8), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9)). The projects share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 30%.

2.3 *Retail* («Jpd Brand Strategy & Design Consultants» (1), «Start Design» (2), «Ziad Al Halabi» (4)). The project's share of at the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 30%.

2.4 *ECommerce* («Webperts» (7), «E Direct» (8), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9)). The project's share at the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 20%.

2.5 *Arts, entertainment & music* («Webperts» (7), «Ziad Al Halabi» (4), «Generator» (10)). The project's share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 10 to 25%.

Group 3 is represented by agencies which deal the projects in such directions as:

3.1 *Hospitality & leisure* («Jpd Brand Strategy & Design Consultants» (1), «Webperts» (7)). The project's share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 10 to 50%.

3.2 *Media* («Webperts» (7), «E Direct» (8)). The projects share of the total agency project's portfolio is from 10 to 25%.

3.3 *Telecommunications* («Start Design» (2), «Webperts» (7)). The projects share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 10 to 20%.

3.4 *Business services* («Ziad Al Halabi» (4), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9)). The project's share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 8 to 25%.

3.5 *Energy & natural resources, Manufacturing* («Jpd Brand Strategy & Design Consultants» (1), «Digital Marketing AgencyTrustCorp» (9)). The project's share of the total agency projects portfolio is from 7 to 15%.

Group 4 is represented by agencies and projects in such directions as:

4.1 *Educational* («Generator» (10)). The project's share at the total portfolio of agency projects is 30%.

The ranking analysis of the project's industry directions of the Ukraine Brand Consultants (Table 8) allowed to determine 6 groups of the agencies. Agency rank (table. 6)

Tab 8: Industry focus Ukrainian Brand Consultants (Jul 2020)

Group	Industry focus	Agency numbers	Agency's rank	Agency's Share, %	Project's share at the total agency's projects portfolio %	
					Min	Max
1	1.1 Business services	7	1,4,5,9,11,12,15	46,7	10	60
2	2.1 Advertising & marketing	5	1,4,6,9,11,12,15	33,3	10	30
3	3.1 Consumer products & services	4	4,7,9,13	26,7	20	50
	3.2 Retail	4	4,6,7,9		10	20
	3.3 Education	4	3,5,6,9		10	20
4	4.1 Real estate	3	3,4,13	20,0	15	30
	4.2 Business services	3	4,12,13		10	40
	4.3 eCcommerce	3	6,9,15		10	40
5	5.1 Information technology	2	11,12	13,3	10	35
	5.2 Arts, entertainment & music	2	1,3		10	10
	5.3 Telecommunications	2	11,12		10	30
	5.4 Media	2	3,15		20	70
6	6.1 Hospitality & leisure	1	9	6,7	10	
	6.2 Energy & natural resources	1	5		20	

	6.3 Manufacturing	1	7		10
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Table is created by authors according to [5]

In particular, among the 15 analyzed agencies, 7 work in the field of Business services. Group 6 corresponds to the smallest number of agencies operating in a particular area.

There are 5 groups of the United Arab Emirates brand consultants corresponding to their service lines focus are determined (Table 9).

Tab 9: Service lines focus United Arab Emirates Brand Consultants (Jul 2020)

Group	Service lines focus	Agency numbers	Agency's rank	Agency's share, %	Project's share at the total agency's projects portfolio %	
					Min	Max
1	1.1 Branding	13	1–13	100	10	100
2	2.1 Web Design	8	1,2,5,7,8,9,10,11	61,5	5	30
3	3.1 Graphic Design	5	1,2,4,6,10	38,5	5	40
	3.2 Web development	5	7,8,9, 12, 13		10	30
	3.3 Social Media Marketing	5	6,8,9,11,12		10	10
4	4.1 Search Engine Optimization	4	8,9,11,12	30,76	10	20
	4.2 Digital Strategy	4	2,5,7		10	15
	4.3 UX/UI Design	4	2,5,7,9		5	30
	4.4 Logo	4	6,10,12, 13		5	20
5	5.1 Pay Per Click	3	8,9,11	23,07	10	20

According to the results of the ranking analysis 5 groups of Ukrainian brand consultants, corresponding to their service lines focus are determined (Table 10).

Tab 10: Service lines focus Ukrainian Brand Consultants (Jul 02.2020)

Group	Service lines focus	Agency numbers	Agency's rank	Agency's share, %	Project's share at the total agency's projects portfolio %	
					Min	Max
1	1.1 Branding	15	1–15	100	10	50
2	2.1 UX/UI Design	9	2,3,5,7,9,10, 11,13,14	60,0	20	50
	2.2 Web Design	8	3,5,6,8, 10, 11,13,15	53,3	20	40
3	3.1 Graphic Design	6	3,4,7,10, 11, 14	40,0	5	30
	3.2 Marketing Strategy	5	1,4,8,12,13	33,3	5	50
4	4.1 Web development	3	9,10,15	20,0	10	70
	4.2 SMM	2	6, 12	13,3	5	20

5	5.1 Direct Marketing	1	12	6,67	40	
	5.2 Search Engine Optimization	1	6		20	
	5.3 E-Commerce Development	1	6		20	
	5.4 Video Productions	1	9		10	20
	5.5 Strategy	1	12		15	
	5.6 Logo	1	10		10	
	5.7 Pay Per Click	1	12		5	
	5.8 Content Marketing	1	12		5	
	5.9 Email Marketing	1	12		5	

The analysis of the group 5 (Table 10), has shown that the players at the brand consultants' market in Ukraine works at such popular services directions as: Direct Marketing (40%), Video Productions (10-20%), E-Commerce Development (20%), Content Marketing (5%), Email Marketing (5%). The main indicators of the top branding UAE and Ukraine companies related to industry and services to identify the subsequent direction for improving their activities are analyzed (Table 11). In the United Arab Emirates most popular industry and services directions for brand consulting are:

- Business services, Consumer products & services, Retail (8,40%);
- Real estate (7,98%); Advertising & marketing (7,56%);
- Health Care and Medical (5,88%); E-commerce, Media (5,46%);
- Financial services, Hospitality & Leisure (4,62%),
- Educational (3,36%); Arts, Entertainment & Music, Automotive (2,52%).

There are also Energy & Natural resources (1,68%); Government, Non Profit (0,84%),

In Ukraine most popular Industry and Services business for brand consulting are:

- Business services (12,75%); Advertising & Marketing (11,54%); Ecommerce (11,16%);
- Consumer products & services (9,96%); Financial services (9,16%);
- Real estate (7,97%); Health Care and Medical (7,57%); Information technology (6,77%)
- Retail (5,58%); Educational (4,38%); Manufacturing, Arts, Entertainment & Music (3,59%); Media (2,79%)

Tab 11: The main indicators of the top branding UAE and Ukraine companies related to industry and services (Jul 2020)

Industry and Services	United Arab Emirates		Ukraine	
	Brand Consultants Numbers	Share, %	Brand Consultants Numbers	Share, %
Advertising & marketing	18	7,56	29	11,55
Arts, entertainment & music	6	2,52	9	3,59
Automotive	6	2,52	–	–
Business services	20	8,40	32	12,75
Consumer products & services	20	8,40	25	9,96
E-commerce	13	5,46	28	11,16
Educational	8	3,36	11	4,38
Energy & natural resources	4	1,68	–	–
Financial services	11	4,62	23	9,16
Government	2	0,84	–	–
Health Care and Medical	14	5,88	19	7,57
Hospitality & leisure	11	4,62	8	3,19
Information technology	16	6,72	17	6,77
Manufacturing	12	5,04	9	3,59

Media	13	5,46	7	2,79
Non Profit	2	0,84	–	–
Others	6	2,52	–	–
Real estate	19	7,98	20	7,97
Retail	20	8,40	14	5,58
Telecommunications	10	4,20	–	–
Numbers of agencies with the relevant information at the website	238	100	251	100
Numbers of agencies at the website	450	–	300	–

Such fields, like: Automotive, Energy & Natural resources, Government, Non Profit (Table 11) have no information or projects [5].

The emphasis of the authors of this article is placed on the consumer, which is the main goal and around which the marketing strategy concerning the brand is to be built. The rank of the top 10 most valuable UAE brands 2020 are [7, Page.86]: «STC», Telecom Providers – Brand value (USD mil) 9,673; «ETISALAT», Telecom Providers – Brand value (USD mil) 5,169; «AL RAJHI BANK», Banks – Brand value (USD mil) 4,732; «FAB», Banks – Brand value (USD mil) 3,918; «EMIRATES», Travel Services – Brand value (USD mil) 2,996; «ALMARAI», Food – Brand value (USD mil) 2,784; «NCB», Banks – Brand value (USD mil) 2,017; «JARIR BOOKSTORE», Retail – Brand value (USD mil) 1,861; «EMAAR», Real Estate – Brand value (USD mil) 1,826; «MOBILY», Telecom Providers – Brand value (USD mil) 1,715.

It is noted, that worst hit industries under COVID-19 are: aviation, oil & gas, tourism & leisure, restaurants, retail [8]. It is carried out that brands, brand management, brand consulting have a number of capabilities and threats when implementing any company that must be considered to minimize possible failures when launching a marketing campaign.

The main cross-category social-communicating and economics trends are:

- refocus of priorities (shifting the customers attention focus from Consumer products and services to medicine). Sales rising of organic food, high-protein ingredients and gluten-free dishes. The world struggles to balance economic pragmatism with medical urgency in these COVID-19 times [7, Pages 69, 70]

- using creativity, sharing experience, have a layer of emotional meaning of the brand, which is what creates a lasting a nity between consumer and brand.

As brands explore the best ways to respect local traditions, they should respect on:

- the stories their brand is telling; affiliation with events that matter; the value of humor in providing some room to maneuver; the importance of authenticity

- combination of traditional marketing communications tools, such as TV and social media, which provide the synergies that can be created between them in order to optimize their returns for brand.

- taking off E-Commerce, because of providing, an experience that matches the balance consumers are trying to strike between time, money and pleasure, having right, relevant, useful range and speedy delivery. By 2025, around 60% of internet users in the UAE will be shopping online [7].

- rise of the omni-shopper. The omni-shopper is more informed, demanding, social, influential and powerful) [7, Pages 74-76]. There main characteristic are: delivering value, the need for speed, experiential retailing, strategizing for the omni-shopper (visibility, right assortment, pricing strategy, promotion strategy).

Conclusions. The consumer identifies himself with some brand based on certain motives and needs. Consumer loyalty to the brand determines the economic success of the brand in the market.

According to the results of the research of industry focus top United Arab Emirates brand consultants is determined, that the most relevant areas are: Information technology, Real estate,

Consumer products and services, Financial services, Advertising & marketing, Retail, Ecommerce, Arts, entertainment & music. All these activities really reflect the specifics of economic environment in the UAE, as a high-tech country that actively uses state-of-the-art information technology. The modern portrait of the UAE is characterized by high-quality consumer goods and services, advertising and marketing, trade, e-commerce. Financial services, real estate, art, entertainment and music deserve special attention.

The most relevant Service lines focus United Arab Emirates are: Branding, Web Design, Graphic Design, Web development, Social Media Marketing. Supportive, more technical areas to the above are: Search Engine Optimization, Digital Strategy, UX / UI Design, Logo, Pay Per Click. The usage of digital media leads to a short-term effect of sales growth. The solution of this problem is balancing brand and sales activation for long-term growth

The most relevant Service lines focus Ukrainian brand consultants are: Business services, Advertising & marketing, Consumer products & services, Retail, Education. Real estate, Financial services, E-Commerce, Information technology, Arts, Entertainment & Music in Ukraine, compared to the UAE, are in the middle of the activity rating, which is negatively affected by economic, social and political factors in Ukraine.

In Ukraine, compared to the UAE, the market of goods and services is imperfect and is in the process of formation and implementation of modern technologies.

In general, at the market of Ukraine and UAE the most popular areas of brand management are: corporate identity, brand strategy, product branding, brand communication (brand communication), naming. We noted that the leading branding agencies Ukraine and UAE are actively working in the field of medium and small business. More than 30% of projects are implemented in big business, which is associated with additional risks. Experts recommend balancing brand building and sales activities – with a 60:40 weighting for B2C and a 54:46 weighting for B2B – is a predictable and evidence-backed formula for sustainable growth [6, 9]. Brand building activities should broadly target all buyers in the category with the goal of providing the critical emotional priming, positioning with memory structures, and brand codes that help prospects decide between different brands. In contrast – but equally as important for driving growth – is sales activation, which can be tightly targeted to hot prospects with rational messages and relevant offers designed to elicit an immediate response [6, 9]. According to the results of the analysis, the optimal set of the main factors is determined and the necessity of increased attention to them by the companies-owners of brands or those who aspire to this status world-wide and, specially, in Ukraine is noted.

Acknowledgements

Prospect of further research in this area will be an analysis of UAE, KSA and European county's place in the international rankings of digital marketing and identification the peculiarities of new customer behavior to the brands according to digitalization.

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